

1 **A formulation for late-stage metastatic breast cancer that has failed all prior treatments.**

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8 The protocol is a palliative care measure. The formulation consists of cytotoxic antibody drug conjugates
9 agents that deliver a toxic payload based on expression of a tumor antigen like TACSTD2 or a tumor
10 kinase like ERBB2/HER2 together with agents that target receptors in the exhaustion and T-cell
11 co-stimulation pathway to invigorate endogenous anti-tumor immunity. The scientific basis or rationale for
12 continued use of chemotherapeutic agents in patients whose disease has progressed following treatment
13 failure is a small probability that the patient will still respond to this regimen through as of yet undefined
14 immune mechanisms that likely entail gain of adaptive function through use of PD1/PDL1 and
15 CTLA4-targeted agents.

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1. Trop-2 ADC: Sacituzumab govitecan (Trodelvy)
 2. Nectin-4 ADC: Enfortumab vedotin
 3. HER2 ADC: regardless of HER2 status.
 - a. T-DM1: trastuzumab emtansine (Kadcyla)
 - b. T-Dxd: trastuzumab deruxtecan (Enhertu)
 4. PD-1: Pembrolizumab (Keytruda)
 5. PD-L1: Durvalumab (Imfinzi) or Atezolizumab (Tecentriq)
 6. CTLA4 : Ipilimumab (Yervoy)